

Challenges in Cloud Adoption among SMEs in the Western Province of Sri Lanka

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Abstract

This study examines the key challenges constraining Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the Western Province of Sri Lanka in adopting cloud computing, focusing on the primary barriers encountered, the influence of organizational readiness, and differences from other developed countries. Guided by an interpretivist paradigm, a qualitative approach was employed to gain in-depth insights from individuals directly involved in cloud-related decision-making. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with nine SME representatives and four cloud industry experts, and thematic analysis was used to identify common themes and patterns. The findings reveal that cloud adoption among Sri Lankan SMEs is hindered by limited technical knowledge, concerns over data security and privacy, high implementation and operational costs, and inadequate technological infrastructure. Internal organizational factors, including leadership involvement, employee digital competencies, and the availability of financial and technical resources, significantly influence organizational readiness and adoption decisions. In addition, context-specific challenges such as language barriers, regulatory uncertainty regarding data protection policies, and weak collaboration between SMEs and cloud service providers further distinguish the Sri Lankan experience from that of more developed countries. The study enhances understanding of cloud adoption challenges in a developing country context and offers practical implications for policymakers to design supportive regulatory frameworks, for SMEs to strengthen leadership and digital capabilities, and for cloud providers to deliver tailored training and collaborative solutions. However, the study is limited to a single province, which may restrict transferability, and future research could expand to other regions and adopt mixed-method approaches to enable broader comparative insights.

Keywords: *cloud adoption, digital transformation, small and medium enterprises*